

Sebastian Kappen: A Challenge for Indian Priests

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Abstract: Sebastian Kappen was a Catholic Jesuit priest who was passionately committed to the poor and down-trodden. This article explores the person that he was, the vision that guided him and the challenge he offers to the Indian priests. The author also outlines the main influences on his life and his impact on the intellectuals of India. His life of commitment to and identification with the poor even at the cost of risking his own life is a commendable challenge to all of us. He was a true humanist who lived and died for the poor and the marginalized.

Keywords: Sebastian Kappen, Passionate humanist, Liberation Theologian, Commitment to the Poor and Marginalised.

Sebastian Kappen (1924-1993) was a Catholic priest who was passionately committed to the poor and down-trodden. This article explores the person that he was, the vision that guided him and the challenge he offers to the Indian priests. His life of commitment to and identification with the poor even at the cost of risking his own life is a commendable challenge to all of us. He was a true humanist who lived and died for the poor and the marginalized.

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Kappen: The Person

Sebastian Kappen (Devasia)¹ was born in a traditional Catholic Syrian family on 4 January 1924 at Kodikulam, Kerala (Kappen, 2013: 10). He was very good in studies and other extracurricular activities in the school.² His passionate search for truth and knowledge brought him to the Jesuit Novitiate at Kozhikode in 1944. His father's parting advice to him was, "Wherever you go, try to excel" (Kappen, 2013: 13). After his formal initial religious formation, he studied philosophy in Shembaganur from 1949 to 1951. After two years of regency, in 1954 he began his theological studies at De Nobili College, Pune, and was ordained a priest in 1957 at the age of thirty-three. He acknowledges that, if he had achieved anything in life, it can be traced back to his Jesuit training (Kappen, 2013: 17).

In 1950s the Marxist ideology was gaining support among the intellectuals in Kerala. The first elected Kerala government was a communist government in 1957. The Jesuit superiors found in Kappen a capable person who would answer to the challenge of communism. After completing the Tertianship, the final stage of Jesuit formation, in 1959 he was sent to do his doctoral studies in Marxism at Pontifical Gregorian University, Rome. The specific topic of his dissertation was: "Religious Alienation and Praxis according to Marx's Economic and Philosophical Manuscripts of 1844." For Kappen, it was a time of intellectual conversion from the essentialistic approach of scholasticism to the existentialistic concerns of Karl Marx (1818-1883) (Kappen, Sebastian. 2002: viii). He finished his doctorate in 1961.

¹ His original name was Devasia, the Malayalam word used for the name Sebastian. After joining the Society of Jesus, the name was changed into Sebastian. See (Kappen, 2013: 17)

² He had collected thirteen first prizes on a school anniversary celebration including those for general proficiency, good conduct, elocution, poetry recitation, long jump, high jump and sprinting.

Kappen: A Model and a Challenge

The popular image of a Catholic theologian is often that of an academically trained theologian who is white, male, ordained and writes theology from a position of institutional authority. Kappen was an exception to this. The purpose of sending him for higher studies in Marxism by his superiors was to defend the Kerala Church from the attack of Communists in Kerala. His studies changed his thinking and attitudes. He neither defended the Church nor opposed Marxism as his superiors expected. Instead, he took the Marxian ideals and Jesus' message into his heart and became a friend and advocate of the poor and the oppressed. He started to live like one among them in the outskirts of the major cities in South India. Let me, examine the 'publicness' in his life, i.e., how much he was related with the ordinary people and in their struggle for survival.

Kappen's first appointment after his return from Rome was as the chaplain of the Newman Association, a movement of learned laity, who often met in local circles to discuss political, social, religious, and other topics at the Lumen Institute in Ernakulam. He had also helped AICUF (All India Catholic University Federation) and SCM (Student Christian Movement) to organize meetings, seminars, study classes and discussions on political, social and religious issues. He used to present papers in seminars organized by religious and non-religious groups. In 1970, he had shifted to Calicut, staying in a house named, *Archana*, and continued his intellectual and public ministry. His life among the poor helped him to deepen his reflections on the ordinary people and the realities of their living conditions. From then, he always chose to live outside Jesuit institutions in order to avoid the comfort and security they ensure, and to imitate Jesus who had always been with the people. At the same time, as a member of the Society of Jesus, he was in contact with the nearest Jesuit house.

In 1972 Kappen returned to Cochin and started to live in a small shed-like house at Kalamassery, the industrial hub of then Kerala. The main aim of his stay was to organize the company workers for their rights. Trade union leaders, students, intellectuals and literary figures used to visit him in the evenings and discussed with him about social, political and religious issues pertaining to Kerala, India and the world. Fr. Joseph Vadakkan (1919-2002), a social activist and Marxist

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supporter, and Fr. Tom Kochery (1940-2014), an organizer of fishermen struggle, were regular visitors to Kappen. Fr. Tom acknowledged that he had learned the basic lessons of Biblical liberative perspectives from Kappen's book *Viswasathil Ninnu Viplavathilekku [From Faith to Revolution]* (Kochery, 2017: 93). Kappen was leading a frugal life like any other ordinary person, doing his cooking, washing and cleaning by himself (Kochery, 2017: 93). He felt that such a life in the midst of the people would help him to insert himself better into the struggles and sufferings of the ordinary people. He used to justify it by saying: 'the way you live, so you think' (Kappen, 2002: ix).

Kappen was a well-accepted professor of theology and philosophy. But he never wanted to become a permanent faculty in any of the seminaries or academic institutions. So he remained a visiting professor to many institutions like, Janan-Deepa Vidyapeth, Pune, Vidyajyothi College of Theology, New Delhi, Maryknoll seminary, Catholic University of Leuven, etc. According to him, theology and philosophy as means, should contribute to establishing or mould a new society from below. He did not want to confine his freedom to the means, i.e., to the joy of mere philosophizing and theologizing.

The sole aim of his theology and philosophy was the liberation of the poor and the marginalized.

Kappen shifted to Chennai in 1975 and lived there till 1983. He settled in a slum area, where the poor and the marginalized people were concentrated. He engaged himself in gathering the youth and teaching them and publishing books and articles. In 1976, he founded the Centre for Social Reconstruction. He worked hard to form a new generation committed to the messages of the historical Jesus and Marx. As a result, many young people, who were engaged in social activities used to come and stay with him in order to learn more about Jesus and Marx. The human suffering that he encountered in Chennai moved him deeply and he wanted to be one with them.

Many of Kappen's guests were passionate social activists and intellectuals. For instance, O. V. Vijayan (1930-2005), novelist, cartoonist and recipient of Padma Bhushan award, was a great friend of Kappen. He said that he learned the basics of Marxism from him (Vijayan, 2017: 90). Sadanand Menon, a nationally reputed art editor, teacher of cultural journalism, recalled the energy and inspiration he received from Kappen (Menon, 2013: 169). Prof. Babu Mathew, trade union leader, social activist, professor of law and Registrar of the National Law School of India, Bangalore, remembers Kappen "as a great teacher, very meticulous, difficult to listen to his lectures without getting completely involved in it. He never spoke in any superficial manner. He would have pondered several hours over every word that he uttered" (Mathew, 2013: 175). Fr. Samuel Rayan remembers him as a man who was always looking for the service of the people, respect their rights, fight for their freedom, bringing them together as a community. Kappen's search for truth helped him to overcome the narrow understanding of Church, religions and political idolatry (Rayan, 2107: 91).

Kappen's writings are a clear example for his commitment to the public causes. He decided to initiate the English journal *Anawim* due to the demand of progressive Christian thinkers and young socially committed activists who had often been engaging in discussion about how Christians should respond to the problems of poverty and injustice in India. The other two journals, *Social Perspectives* (1978-1982), and *Negations* (1982-1985), also started with the same intention. His book, *Jesus and Freedom*, was the outcome of decade-long reflections and discussions on Christian life and faith. The purpose of his writings was to conscientize people to work for the establishment of a counter-cultural society.

Kappen's health gradually deteriorated due to poor life and continued stress. In 1991, he had the first heart attack while giving a talk on the First Gulf War. He was afflicted with asthma, spondylosis, and high blood pressure as well. In the same year he had the second heart attack and the doctors prescribed a heart surgery. Kappen refused to undergo the surgery by saying, "I have decided not to go for surgical test and bypass surgery, since such expensive treatments were unaffordable to the majority of the people" (Vattamattom, 2018: 18). He died on 30 November 1993 due to heart attack. This shows his commitment and identification with the poor even at the cost of risking his own life in health matters. He was a true humanist who lived and died for the poor and the marginalized.

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